

A STUDY OF WARP-KNITTED FABRIC STRUCTURE PARAMETERS AFFECTING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TEXTILE-REINFORCED CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

In this work, twelve samples of warp-knitted reinforced fabric and concrete from four different types of reinforced rovings (glass and three carbon rovings) were fabricated. The results of investigations on the three common types of warp-knit stitches i.e., tricot, cord and pillar are presented. The samples were tested for mechanical properties to determine the basic characteristics for reinforced fabrics and concrete. In addition, the shape of the roving cross section was assessed as a function of the type of the stitch. The obtained results indicate that the stitch type exerts a significant effect on the mechanical properties of the reinforced concrete and the roving cross section shape. For a given type of roving, the mechanical properties of concrete with tricot and cord stitches are greater than that of concrete with the pillar stitch. The main factor affecting the properties of concrete was found to be the cross-section shape of the roving in the reinforced fabric, which due to its flattening in the case of fabrics with tricot and cord stitches or compactness in the case of the fabrics with the pillar stitch, affected the transfer of mechanical load across the roving cross-section. In addition, the strength of the original rovings used for the fabric making significantly affected the retention of the strength of the reinforced fabric and concrete.

1 INTRODUCTION

High-performance textiles are widely used in structural and civil engineering applications as reinforcements in structural composites. Various textile structures, such as short fibers, yarns, rovings and fabrics, which differ in the manufacturing process, are used as reinforcements in concrete parts. Textile reinforced concrete is characterized by its broad range in mechanical properties, high handling potential and production capability [1-5]. High-strength yarns used for producing the reinforced fabrics are continuous filament yarns without twist, consisting usually of a few hundreds or thousands of individual filaments. In the manufacture of high-strength reinforcing materials for concrete, mainly yarns such as alkali resistant (AR) glass and carbon are used. These types of fibres have very high mechanical characteristics (tensile strength, modulus, etc.) and display high potential as concrete reinforcements because of their adequate mechanical performance and durability in alkali environments.

One of the most important parameters affecting the properties of cementitious composites is the geometrical characteristics of reinforcing structure. The given geometry may improve the bonding at the reinforcement-matrix interface. The bonding of straight yarns with cement systems is relative poor [6]. It may be enhanced by using the special yarn or fabric structures and increase the efficiency of reinforcement. The factors that determine the properties of yarn and fabrics, and the cementitious composites are determined by the structure in yarn cross section and along the yarn length or fabric pattern. Peled et al. [7] found that the flexural strength of cement-based composites depend the fabric

structure. They studied the effect of the geometry of woven plain weave fabrics with varied fills density on the bond between monofilament polyethylene yarns and cement matrix. It was found that the yarn and woven fabric structures have a significant influence on increasing the bond between the woven fabric and the cementitious matrix [8]. The fiber–matrix microstructure was also analyzed by optical microscopy in [9]. Microstructural features for the different fiber type were characterized and correlated with their mechanical properties. The microscopy observations on specimen cross-sections showed that distribution and compact of filament bundles has an effect on bond strength and cement penetrability between the filaments. More open bundle leads to better characteristics. The filaments distributions in bundles were qualified by simple terms like ‘more compact’ and ‘more open’. However, the results of such analysis depend largely on the subjective opinion of the person doing the testing.

Textile fabric reinforcements come in the forms of woven, non-woven, and knitted structures, which differ in their manufacturing process. Knitting is one of the most versatile technologies of production for textile fabrics. Warp-knitted fabrics with the directly inserting yarn oriented specifically along the direction at which forces arise are suitable as concrete reinforcements. In the manufacturing of warp-knitted fabrics, directly oriented high-strength yarns are inserted in the machine in longitudinal (warp) and transverse (weft) directions [10, 11]. The reinforced yarns are then combined by knitting yarn. The structure and properties of the inlay yarns are influenced by loop length, knitting yarn tension, and the stitching pattern [5, 12, 13]. The stitching pattern in the warp-knitted fabrics determines the geometry of the cell of the fabric structure. Typically two groups of knitting stitches, namely pillar and tricot stitches are used in the warp-knitting process for manufacturing of technical fabrics. In the pillar stitch, the same guide always overlaps the same needle [14]. In the tricot stitch, the underlaps connect both the courses and the wales. In the simplest of this group, one yarn crosses between the adjacent wales in a tricot stitch (1×1 lap). Two yarns cross between the wales in a cord stitch (2×1 lap). In the pillar stitch, the same guide always overlaps the same needle. The chains of loops connected together by the underlaps in unconnected wales are produced [14]. Geometrically, the difference between the tricot stitch and cord stitch is expressed in the angle of the underlap with respect to vertical axis, which in the cord stitch is greater than that in the tricot stitch, as shown in Fig. 1a and 1b, respectively. In the pillar stitch, all underlaps are oriented along the vertical axis, as shown in the Fig. 1c.

Figure 1: Warp-knitted fabrics of glass rovings with tricot (a), cord (b) and pillar stitches (c) as reinforcements in concrete.

Janetzko et al. [13] showed that the yarns in warp-knitted fabrics with tricot stitch have a flat ribbon shaped cross section that provides the increase in the contact length between the filaments and the concrete. According to Roy et al., [15] warp-knitted fabrics with a tricot pattern show higher load-bearing capacity than specimens reinforced with a pillar stitch. Zhou et al. [16] showed that the basic stitches of a multiaxial warp-knitted structure are important factors that can influence the mechanical properties of the structure.

This work aims to develop fabrics with common stitch types and investigate their mechanical characteristics because the resulting strength of the textiles is important for designing textile reinforced concrete parts.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

For the experiment, alkali resistant (AR) glass roving and 3 different types of carbon rovings were chosen. To investigate the influence of the raw material different in precursor materials, polyacrylonitrile based fibers (PAN) and pitch based carbon fibers were used. Table 1 lists an overview of the properties of reinforcing rovings considered in this study. Polyester multifilament yarn (16.7 Tex) was used as the knitting yarn.

Sample designation	Roving	Filament count, type	Linear density, Tex
GR	Glass roving	Alkali-resistant	2400
CR-1	Carbon roving (1)	24K, PAN-based	1600
CR-2	Carbon roving (2)	24K, PAN-based	810
CR-3	Carbon roving (3)	12K, Pitch-based	1560

Table 1: Roving specifications.

2.2 Fabrics

For the experiments, twelve types of warp-knitted fabrics were produced on a 6 gage warp-knitting machine (MALIMO/c/P2-2S, Karl Mayer Textilmaschinenfabrik GmbH) at the Institute fuer Textiltechnik (ITA) of the RWTH Aachen University with different specifications in terms of the materials and the stitching pattern used. AR-glass and carbon rovings were used as the warp inlay yarns, while the weft yarns were glass rovings only. The samples contain three rovings per inch of fabric width. The warp-knitted fabrics names are combined as follows: GR (glass roving) or (CR) carbon roving – used roving material; 1/2/3 – roving type; T (tricot)/C (cord)/P (pillar) – knitting pattern.

2.3 Composite preparation

The warp-knitted fabrics were integrated at the top and bottom faces of concrete samples (5 mm from each side). The preparation of the concrete was done in the mold (30 mm thick). In order to achieve good penetration of concrete with reinforced fabrics the fine grain concrete was chosen. The mix proportion of fine grain concrete is given in the Table 2. The specimens were demolded after 1 day and tested at the age of 28 days.

Portland cement	Fly ash	Sand (0-0.25 mm)	Sand (0.2-0.6 mm)	Plasticizer	Silica fume	Water
490	175	499	714	7	70	245

Table 2: The constitutes of fine grained concrete (kg/m³)

2.4 Tensile testing of the roving and fabric samples

The tensile properties of the rovings were investigated using a Zwick universal testing machine (model Z100). The roving samples were prepared according to the test method developed at the Institute fuer Textiltechnik. The free ends of the specimen were clamped in a rubber mold and aligned with mild tension. The embedding of the roving ends was ensured by applying epoxy resin into the mold. The specimens were left undisturbed until testing, which was carried out on the following day. The rovings were tested to failure with a test speed of 10 mm/min and a gage length of 125 mm.

The tensile properties of the warp-knitted fabrics were determined by a standard method termed as strip test. The free ends of the fabric specimens were fixed with pieces of carton paper and embedded with epoxy resin to avoid the damaging of brittle rovings. The stress-strain diagrams were obtained with a 100 mm sample base and clamp movement of 10 mm/min. Tensile stress was determined as the

maximum applied force divided by the initial cross sectional area of the specimen using the following equation.

$$\sigma = \frac{F\gamma}{Tn} \quad (1)$$

n is a number of rovings in the cross sectional area of the specimen.

2.5 Flexural testing of the concrete samples

The flexural properties of the composite specimens were determined by four point bending test. The specimens with dimensions of 30×60×180 mm were cut. The flexural tests were carried out in a Zwick Z100 testing machine at a clear span of 60 mm. Crosshead rate was 1 mm/min.

2.6 Analysis of the roving cross section

The samples of the roving cross sections were examined by optical microscopy. The specimens were cut and polished to achieve a high accuracy of recognition. The micrographs were captured using an optical microscope (Leica type DM 4000 M) equipped with a digital camera and the filaments in roving cross section were recognized using a co-ordinate system. An optical micrograph and the coordinate assignment of the cross section of the carbon roving are shown in Fig. 2a and 2b respectively.

Figure 2: Optical micrograph of a cross section of glass roving (a) and its coordinate assignment (b).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile properties of the fabric samples

The tensile strength and Young's modulus values were plotted as histograms and are shown in Fig. 3a and 3b for glass and carbon fabrics. As can be seen from the data obtained, the type of the stitch significantly affects the tensile properties of the warp-knitted fabrics. The tensile strengths of the warp-knitted structures of glass roving (GR) with the tricot stitch and the pillar stitch are slightly higher (by about 14%) than the glass fabric with the cord stitch (Fig. 3a). The plot of the Young's modulus for glass fabrics showed a similar character (Fig. 3b) reaching a maximum value for the sample with the tricot stitch which was about 11% greater than the fabric with the cord stitch.

Samples of warp-knitted structures of carbon rovings CR1 and CR3 demonstrate similar behavior depending on the stitch pattern. The samples with the tricot stitch showed the maximum tensile strength for all three carbon rovings (Fig. 3a). Samples with a cord stitch showed a lower tensile strength than that with the tricot stitch. In the case of sample CR1-C, the tensile strength decreased by 8% and the tensile strength was lower than 14% for sample CR2-C in comparison to that of the sample with the tricot stitch. The reduction in the tensile strength of the sample CR3-C was insignificant. The

samples of the fabrics with pillar stitch showed even lower tensile strengths (values of CR1-P, CR2-P and CR3-P were lower by 21%, 7% and 14.4%, respectively, in comparison to the values shown by CR1-T, CR2-T and CR3-T). Sample CR2-P was the only exception, which exhibited a higher strength than the fabric with the cord stitch. As shown in Fig. 3b, the stitch type did not affect the modulus of the sample CR1. The dependence of the Young's modulus of the stitch type in the case of samples CR2 and CR3 is similar to gradation noticed for tensile strength. The maximum Young's modulus was achieved for the sample CR2. Moreover, the Young's modulus for the fabrics with the tricot and pillar stitches for sample CR2 were about 14% higher in comparison to the corresponding sample with the cord stitch. In the case of the sample CR3, the difference between the Young's moduli of the fabrics with tricot and pillar stitches was 25%.

Figure 3: Effect of the stitch pattern on the tensile properties of warp-knitted fabrics.

By analyzing the results, it can be concluded that for fabrics with the cord and pillar stitches, the underlaps are longer in comparison to the fabric with a tricot stitch in which the angle of the underlap is midway between the angles taken by pillar and cord stitches. This leads to more rapid tightening of the knitting yarn and prevents further stretching for fabrics. For fabric with tricot stitch, the midway position of the underlap angle allows for the higher deformation of the rovings.

3.2 Flexural characteristics of the concrete samples

The flexural strength values for glass and carbon fabrics reinforced concrete were plotted as histograms and are shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen from the data obtained, the type of the stitch affects the flexural strength of the concrete samples. The flexural strengths of the concrete sample of the glass fabric with the tricot stitch GR-T are higher (by about 14%) than with the cord stitch and (by about 19%) than the pillar stitch. The samples of carbon rovings CR1 with the tricot stitch showed the maximum flexural strength. Samples with a cord stitch showed a lower flexural strength than that with the tricot stitch. In the case of sample CR1-C, the flexural strength decreased by 6.5% and the tensile strength was lower than 25% for sample CR1-P in comparison to that of the sample with the tricot stitch. Concrete sample of roving CR2 demonstrate similar behavior depending on the stitch pattern. The samples with cord and pillar stitched showed even lower tensile strengths, values of CR2-C and CR2-P were lower by 6.3% and 36%, respectively, in comparison to the values shown by CR2-T. Concrete sample of roving CR3 was the only exception, which exhibited a higher strength with the cord stitch. The reduction in the tensile strength of the sample CR3 was insignificant.

3.3 Cross-section observations

The shape of the inlay roving in the fabric is mainly formed during knitting and is determined by the stitch type. Analysis of the roving cross section in the fabric and in the concrete samples revealed significant differences in their shapes. The coordinate assigned model of the cross sections observed in

each type of the stitch in the case of GR and CR1 rovings are shown in Fig. 5. As seen from the models of the rovings, in fabrics with tricot (Fig. 5a) and cord stitches (Fig. 5b), the cross section is flattened. The limited length of the underlap in the tricot stitch (1×1 lap) leads to a higher degree of tightening of the yarn. The cross section of the cord stitch takes a hemi-elliptical symmetrical shape because of the longer underlap (2×1 lap) than that in the tricot stitch. The cross section of the pillar stitch (Fig. 5c) acquires an elliptical, almost circular shape on account of the orientation of the knitting yarn in the direction of applied force and because of the tightening around the reinforced yarn.

Figure 4: Effect of the stitch pattern on the flexural strength warp-knitted fabric reinforced concrete.

The results of the roving cross sectional shapes provide cues to explain the differences in the results seen in the mechanical tests. In most cases, the maximum strength was achieved in samples with tricot stitch, which may be attributed mainly to the flattened shape of the cross sections, its uniform expansion and, as a consequence, better force transmission between the filaments of the roving during straining. An almost circular shape attained in samples with the pillar stitch provides a lower transfer of mechanical load through the bundle of filaments because of their uneven working in tension and friction between filaments.

Figure 5: Coordinate assigned models of the cross sections of glass roving (left) and carbon roving (right) with tricot stitch (a), cord stitch (b) and pillar stitch (c).

3.4 Effect of the roving and stitch type

The efficiency of textile reinforcement depends on the use of the properties of the original rovings with various characteristics. One of the main characteristics determining the suitability of the use of a fabric for reinforcement may be strength retention factors. This indicates the use of the roving properties in the fabric depending on the effect of the stitching pattern. The latter factor has significant influence on the retention properties in the light of damage of brittle yarns during textile processing. The relationship between the tensile strength of the reinforcing rovings and the corresponding fabric and concrete properties are shown in Fig. 6a and 6b, respectively. In these plots, the tensile strength of the rovings is on the axes of the abscissas, and on the axis of the ordinate, the tensile strength of the fabrics and the flexural strength of concrete made of these rovings are plotted. The sloping dashed line drawn at an angle of 45° indicates complete translation of the roving properties in the fabrics (Fig. 6a). Ideally, all points should be located as close as possible to this line. As seen from the data for the strength retention, the glass roving shows highest retention of strength in samples with all types of stitches (85-98% of the original roving strength). All carbon samples lie below this line. With increase in the strength of the carbon roving, the translation of strength from the roving to the fabric reduces. Hence, the glass roving demonstrates the highest level of property retention. For carbon rovings, the highest tensile retention values were observed in sample CR-1, 87.6%, 80.9% and 69.1% for fabrics with the tricot, cord, and pillar stitch, respectively. The lowest strength retention (only 65-76%) was observed for sample CR2. This could be attributed to the fact that CR2 shows the highest stiffness among the carbon rovings, leading to high brittleness and low properties after textile processing.

Figure 6: Roving utilization properties in the fabrics (a) and concrete (b).

A similar dependence was observed for the roving strength properties in concrete (Fig. 6b). As seen from the results, the tensile strength of the original rovings is not always a key factor for selecting reinforcing rovings. The glass roving demonstrates very good level of property utilization in the concrete. The utilization of the strength in the carbon rovings worsened and decreased with increase in the tensile strength of the constituting original rovings. For example, a roving with a lower tensile strength (sample CR3) shows highest flexural strength in concrete, providing almost the same flexural strength in concrete as sample CR2 on account of lower losses in textile processing. The lower extent of translation of properties can be explained by the high brittleness of the carbon rovings and with increase in the strength and stiffness of rovings, partial destruction of the filament occurs during straining, exerting a significant influence on their tensile properties. It can be seen that the reinforcement efficiency depends on the tensile properties of the constituting original rovings and knitting pattern. We conclude that it is possible to reduce the cost of the raw materials by using original rovings constituting the fabrics with lower tensile characteristics but with higher retention properties in the fabric.

4 CONCLUSIONS

One of the most important parameters affecting the properties of cementitious composites is the geometrical characteristics of reinforcing structure. In this work, we present the results of our investigations on the three common types of warp-knit stitches i.e., tricot, cord and pillar. For the experiment, alkali resistant (AR) glass roving and 3 different types of carbon rovings were chosen. Twelve samples of warp-knitted fabric and concrete samples were produced. The warp-knitted fabrics were integrated at the top and bottom faces of concrete samples. In order to achieve good penetration of concrete with reinforced fabrics the fine grain concrete was chosen. The tensile properties of the rovings and the warp-knitted fabrics were determined. The flexural properties of the composite specimens were determined by four point bending test. The samples of the roving cross sections depending on stitch type were examined by optical microscopy.

The results revealed that the stitch type exerted a significant effect on the tensile properties of the fabrics, the roving cross section shape, and the composites. The main factor affecting the properties is the cross section shape of the roving of in the fabric, which due to its flattening in the case of fabrics with tricot and cord stitches or compactness in the case of the fabrics with the pillar stitch, affects the transfer of mechanical load across the roving cross section. On the basis of obtained results, the recommendation on the optimal application of the developed fabrics as concrete reinforcement and the possibility of reducing the cost of the raw materials by making reinforcing fabrics with using original rovings of lower tensile characteristics, which result in higher retention properties in the concrete, are provided.

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